

Best Practices of Affordable Housing in India

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Abstract

In India affordable housing is a major problem in India. It is an estimated that 18 million houses are shortage out of which 99% are economically weaker sections of society. This paper is an attempt to reveal the best practices of affordable housing in India and across the world and recommendation of affordable housing in the best possible way. The institution and agencies are responsible for formulation and implanting affordable housing policies in the state.

Introduction

Affordable Housing is center stage of agenda in national as well as international level. Housing is a basic need of human being next to food and cloth; the government has to provide access to for its every citizenry to increase their productive capital. That role and function, it is positive impacted in society in many dimension access to infrastructure, employment, household wealth, health, education, poverty levels, maternal and women participation in the workforce and many other well- being indicators. India seeks to improve its living conditions in a big way; access to the affordable housing becomes the first major stumbling block for its citizens. This article address how to overcome the issue of affordable housing and the best practices of affordable housing market in India and policy interventions required to make it better.

Best practices of Affordable Housing Field-based credit assessment

The credit assessment process is more crucial in case of self-employed and informal categories, but in case of salaried borrowers, it is normally two or three days is taken for collection of income tax proofs, CIBIL credit check, analysis of statement of equity and banking behaviour, preparation of computer aided manufacturing to appraisal and approval. Though Self-employed borrowers shall not having proper monthly income as their earnings

Similarly in the case of informal sector may not have income/tax/banking documentation and also they are working in the various work area, and the income generation capability of each work is different. Therefore, the credit assessment process needs to be more dynamic. HFC has to change the present operating models and ensure business delivery yet adherence to risk management. HFCs officer required to visit personally to understand to their client's repaying capacity for his nature of work , flow of income patterns, monthly commitments, saving, attitude/lifestyle/ habits. It is advised to deploy one or more field officer for evaluate repayment capacity and genuine willingness to repay.

Pretaining Quality Credit Appraisal Staff and Training

It is a very complicated process of initiate the viability of lending to low- income or self - employed borrowers, the credit officer's role are critical. It is advised that to concentrate top line salary people and bringing genuine borrowers for quick claim of premium for their quality work. HFCs need to benchmark/document the best-practice process of experienced officers which can help training the newer, fresh recruits who will naturally come at a lower price.

Early-Warning Systems in the Collection Process

Monitoring the default payment is another key area in case of low income borrowers/ informal sector; the repayment frequency can be weekly or fortnightly, instead of monthly. It will increase cash inflow recovery very faster. It is suggested that during defaults, the credit officer who visits their client house personally, if find genuine reason the loan might be restructured by extending the tenure.

Marketing Methods should be Easier

Home buyer can get clarification about their documentation process with help of home loan counsellors at the office. It is very easy to apply for home loan product at the same time. Other types of marketing techniques are radio, television, newspaper, online advertising, and banners behind buses/autorikshaws which they can easy to access relevant information

Project Risk

In order to avoid risk of the project. The HFCs has to appoint legal and technical officers to checks on the property to ensure it is free of litigation, hindrance ect. Smaller HFCs offered outsource this function to specialist providers. This practice helps to build potential home buyers and giving them a comfort factor in terms of free risky project.

The Decentralized Operational Work

The corporate office has to decentralise operational work into various branches. Each braches is responsible for appraisal, paperwork and collection work. The branches have to interact with the client directly with credit appraiser, customer service staff. Each braches have accountable on the prospective volume. The corporate offices have to fix responsibility, accountability and monitoring of operation for their branches.

Guarantor of Loan

Guarantor of loan is important while lending to the informal sector. It mirrors the rationale behind using the concept in microfinance a proxy for collateral, since social pressure might get customers to repay loans. HFC is working with reputed lenders to provide loan programs based on the partial guarantee.

Conclusion

Affordable housing is a major driving segment in India. As the supply of affordable housing and finance has amplified, the gap between supply and demand is still huge, spelling a significant opportunity. Excellence in best practices of operational processes like appraisal/collection hold the key to the business' success and helps to access housing finance very easy. The government policy should concentrate for economically weaker section of the society for access of affordable housing with microfinance level and to promote smooth functioning loan process with help of the above discussed best practices of affordable housing.

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